

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Stakeholders' opinions on the agricultural practices applied in cereal cultivation in the Lusitanian area and proposals for improvement.

The survey developed by the SoildiverAgro project sought to identify the most relevant current agri-environmental problems of wheat cultivation and the priority needs of end-users in order to assess the practical potential for integrating more sustainable farming practices in different farming systems. In Galicia, farmers, agricultural technical advisors and other stakeholders such as researchers or administrators responded to the survey, a total of 73 people with an average age of 45.8 years. The most serious problems identified were low and variable yields, inadequate farm drainage, low soil fertility and high pest and disease pressure. In this respect, increasing soil fertility, mobilising nutrients during crop development, reducing the incidence of pests and diseases, as well as improving biodiversity

and soil structure were the most important priorities identified by respondents. Minimal and shallow tillage, addition of organic matter and use of green manures or maintenance of vegetation cover were proposed by most respondents as the most effective farming practices. In addition, crop diversification, pesticide use and tillage were identified as the most effective farming practices for pest and disease control. However, farmers' lack of knowledge about their efficacy, adaptability, management and cost-effectiveness could hinder their application. Therefore, there is a need to research, advise and keep farmers informed in order to steer agriculture towards profitable and sustainable production systems.

1. Wheat plants in leaf development.

KEYWORDS

Farming practices, soil conservation, stakeholder's assessment, technology adoption, wheat crop.

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